

Complementary research infrastructures for future-proof social policy: GUIDE, GGP, SHARE and ESS

Demographic changes demand a broadened view on public policy. Adopting a 'life course perspective' enriches the elaboration and evaluation of new policy measures. Social challenges such as population aging and current housing crises have different effects on citizens depending on the life stage they are in. Moreover, the costs and benefits of specific behaviours do not necessarily sink in simultaneously or in the same domain of life. Investments in education, for example, generally do not pay off until later in a person's life. The same holds true for public policy. The effects of policy choices in one domain, say investments in the accessibility of childcare, are perceived in other policy domains, such as a higher rate of female labour force participation.

IMPORTANCE OF A LIFE COURSE PERSPECTIVE FOR SOCIAL POLICY

Influential factors such as upbringing, education, choice of partner(s), general health and personal beliefs help determine people's life course. Whereas the life course of some people shows a high degree of stability, the lives of most people are characterized by consecutive phases marked by major events and role changes. From a scientific and a societal perspective, it is relevant to understand differences between groups of people in the way their lives unfold. It is important to pay attention to the role of agency and the process of aging, but also to the influence of (geographical) place, (historical) time or timing and intergenerational ties.

ADDED VALUE OF GUIDE, GGP, SHARE AND ESS

International research infrastructures that use survey data jointly map citizens' lives, from childhood to old age. GUIDE, GGP, SHARE and ESS, together provide key insights into different phases and transitions in individuals' lives, as well as the overarching attitudes and beliefs that people develop throughout their life. 'Open-access' data and published reports support evidence-based policy and facilitate long-term thinking. In addition, these four research infrastructures provide tools for forward-looking policies related to social services, housing, health care and the functioning of democracy. The quality of GUIDE, GGP, SHARE and ESS is evidenced through their recognition by the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI). GGP and Guide are included as 'projects' in the ESFRI Roadmap 2021, while SHARE and ESS have long enjoyed 'landmark' status.

MUTUAL REINFORCEMENT AND SUSTAINED COOPERATION

GUIDE, GGP, SHARE and ESS complement each other, both in content and in the execution of (research) activities. GUIDE collects data on experiences during childhood and adolescence, using a developmental perspective. GGP data describe the lives of (young) adults with special attention for the dynamics within families and at the population level. SHARE focuses on the lives of older people (50+) with a focus on their behaviours, well-being and health. The ESS collects data across the life course among a representative sample of those aged 15 years or older. It focuses on their attitudes and beliefs as well as their social condition. Together, GUIDE, GGP, SHARE and ESS have an undeniable impact on scientific innovation and social policy. Among other things, GUIDE, GGP, SHARE and ESS are leading infrastructures for cross-national research in the social sciences and beyond. Thanks to rich databases of reports and policy briefs, these research infrastructures are also pillars in the information supply of policy makers and stakeholders in the fields of youth (care), families, housing, demography, health, retirement, elderly (care) and citizenship.

This complementarity provides opportunities for mutual reinforcement. For example, GGP and ESS are leading the way in the transition to online (web-based) data collection. From this pioneering role, experiences and best practices can be shared with the other research infrastructures. SHARE specializes in measuring health developments over longer periods of time. Thanks to its focus on experiences during childhood and adolescence, GUIDE, an infrastructure that is presently being built, completes the overarching picture of the life course as a whole. These four infrastructures are also collaborating in European funded projects and are jointly promoting the use of social science data for evidence-based policies. Countries' participation in GUIDE, GGP, SHARE and ESS provides a solid basis for future-proof social policy.

PROFILE OF EACH RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

GROWING UP IN DIGITAL EUROPE (GUIDE)

'Growing Up In Digital Europe' (GUIDE) will be Europe's first international comparative birth cohort study focused on child and adolescent well-being. The main objective is to monitor children's personal development and psychosocial growth over time. As part of this monitor, crucial information will be collected on children's family situations, the neighbourhoods they grow up in and the schools they attend. These data will allow researchers from different disciplines to study children's well-being over a longer period of time. In addition, the experiences of children in different EU countries can be compared.

GUIDE is included as a 'project' in the ESFRI Roadmap 2021. It is headquartered at University College Dublin in Dublin (IE). GUIDE will grow over the next few years to become an important source of reliable information for developing social policies for children, youth and families across Europe.

THE GENERATIONS AND GENDER PROGRAMME (GGP)

The Generations and Gender Program (GGP) is the only, internationally comparative research infrastructure focused on demographic trends and social dynamics within families. Through the Generations and Gender Survey (GGS), new information is collected on the lives of (young) adults, people aged 18-79. These representative data are enriched with descriptive indicators for the national context. Important topics that can be studied using data from the GGP are partner choice, family formation, the division of labour within households, intergenerational relationships, and the socioeconomic conditions of young adults, families, and other household types. In addition, the GGP provides information for the purposes of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Indicators of gender autonomy and the use of contraception are measured repeatedly within the program.

The Generations and Gender Programme (GGP) was founded in 2000 and is run by a consortium of international knowledge institutions. The GGP is headquartered at the Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute (NIDI) in The Hague (NL). In 2021, the GGP was included as a project in the ESFRI Roadmap. By now, more than 30 countries have collected data through the GGS. The GGP database contains reliable information on more than 300,000 individuals. Worldwide, the GGP has more than 5,000 users who together produce a rich source of up-to-date knowledge.

The Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE-ERIC)

'The Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe' (SHARE) collects data among people aged 50+, providing insights into their health and socioeconomic situation at later stages of life. SHARE is the richest source of information for country comparative research on the consequences of aging. By tracking the well-being of older individuals over time, determinants of poor health and financial vulnerability can be identified.

SHARE is coordinated centrally from its headquarters in Berlin (DE). SHARE has been on the ESFRI roadmap since 2006. Through questionnaires, SHARE collects a diverse set of information about older people. These include a detailed medical history, as well as subjective and objective measurements of current health and cognitive impairment. It also collects information on social networks and contacts, work situation and retirement as well as financial situation, including retirement income, assets and costs associated with health and care. Since 2004, more than 600,000 in-depth interviews have been conducted with more than 160,000 people from 27 European countries and Israel.

The European Social Survey (ESS-ERIC)

The European Social Survey (ESS) maps the attitudes, beliefs, behaviours and social condition of European citizens. These survey data can be supplemented by specific information on the national context. This makes the ESS an excellent source of information for studying change or stability in the opinions of cross-sections of national populations, as well as for comparing the populations of different European countries. The ESS focuses on residents aged 15 years and older in around 30 countries. Thanks to this broad approach, this research infrastructure provides data on citizens at all stages of the life course. This provides the opportunity to compare attitudes, beliefs, behaviour and the social condition of different age groups within populations.

The ESS has existed since 2001 and is headquartered at City University of London (UK). ESS questionnaires are administered every two years. Each round of data collection is based on a new randomly drawn sample. In total, the ESS provides researchers with access to responses to more than 18,000 questions.

Topics covered in the ESS include social and public trust; political interest and participation; socio-political orientations; media use; moral, political and social values; social exclusion and national, ethnic and religious loyalties. More recently ESS launched its on-line panel CRONOS to provide additional services to academics and policy makers.

